

MODELING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING SYSTEMS

Takeshi Takatoya¹, Isao Kimpara² and Kazuro Kageyama²

*¹Airframe Division, National Aerospace Laboratory,
7-44-1 Jindaiji Higashimachi, Chofu-shi, Tokyo 182, Japan*

*²Division of Engineering, The University of Tokyo,
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113, Japan*

SUMMARY: The present paper aims at developing computer aided design and manufacturing systems for laminated composite structures, in order to achieve light-weight structures. As laminated panels were made by layup process step by step, laminated composite structures are handled not only as materials, which modeling is used in general purpose systems, but also as stratum structures. Then a new model of laminated composite structures is proposed in the present paper, which modeling is based on object oriented inheritance concept. According to the new modeling, some prototypes of CAD/CAE/CAM systems are developed and demonstrated. It shows that the developed systems are effective in designing lamination, analyzing laminated panels with finite element analysis and assisting of manufacturing tool mold.

KEYWORDS: modeling, CAD/CAE/CAM, object-oriented language, shell structure, light-weight structure, design methodology, layerwise analysis, tool mold manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

Advanced Composite Materials (ACM), such as Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP), have recently been applied to shell structures which are required stiffness and strength for out-plane pressure and light-weight. For example, shell structures are America's cup challenging yachts, wing panels of small aircraft and so on. ACM have a big potential for archiving a light-weight structure, however, material design, structural design and fabrication technology should nearly be entangled in achieving a significant weight saving.

In design process of composite structures, material design, structure design and manufacturing process design are closely related with each other. Then, many design simulations are involved, such as selections and combinations of constituent materials, determinations of fiber orientation angles, determinations of laminate stacking sequences, choices of failure criteria, determinations of cutting and layup plans and so on [1].

It should be efficient to apply computer systems in the design process, however, the conventional CAD/CAE systems are not suited for the design of composite structures in the point of design flexibility. Because they have been developed mainly for isotropic materials, anisotropic laminated materials have been put in an additional position [2]. For this reason,

the present paper insists that computer aided design and manufacturing systems for composite structures have need to be developed.

MODELING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

In order to develop computer aided design and manufacturing systems for laminated composite structures, a new model of laminated composite materials is required. The conventional modeling which are applied in conventional CAD/CAE systems, take laminated materials as only material data for each finite element. This modeling involves two problems. One is that lamination would be dependent on finite elements as shown in Figure 1. The other is that stacking sequences would be converted to different materials. This cause many materials in the structures.

As laminated materials were made by layup process step by step and laminated materials were put together to structures, laminated composite structures should be handled not only as materials but also as stratum structures. In the present paper, laminated composite structures consist of five stratum, that is, fiber and matrix as base materials, lamina, ply, laminated structure, main structure as shown in Figure 2. Lamina is composed of fiber and matrix, which means that lamina has thickness, strength and modulus as single-ply plate. Ply means that lamina is defined on tool mold with some area and fiber direction. Laminated structure consists of plies with stacking sequence. After laminated structures are treated as stratum structures in the computer systems, a designer can easily make models of laminated structures according to the images.

CONCEPTS AND CONSTRUCTIONS OF DEVELOPING A SYSTEM

It is one of purposes in the present paper, that computer systems are developed by using of the new model. Figure 3 shows a flowchart of laminate design and process design. The computer aided design and manufacturing systems should have three characteristic points, as follows: laminate definition easily and high response to design change, layerwise structural analysis and evaluation easily and making tool mold accurately.

LAMINATE DEFINITION AND DESIGN CHANGE

A mold is necessary for curing laminate plates. It is considered two ways in the coordinates with which laminate plates are defined. One is global coordinates, the other is surface oriented coordinates which are origin on the mold. A designer define a laminate concerned with direction of fiber as surface oriented coordinates and laminated area as global coordinates. As coordinates are converted each other in the systems as shown in Figure 4, a ply is defined easily with some area and fiber direction.

It is important to change design easily in the point of design spiral. The adaptation of the new model made it possible to response easily to design change in the developed systems. The indispensable data should be used properly in design, analysis and manufacturing with the use of scope controls.

In the present paper, the developed systems were suggested to be programmed by object-oriented language C++ [3]. It is possible that laminate stratum structures are defined accurately by classes and class inheritances in object-oriented languages, and it is easy to change laminate design by replacement of classes.

LAYERWISE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION

After definition of laminates, it is efficient to analyze structures by means of finite element methods. Since finite element meshes belong to the laminated structure model, design change requires regeneration of meshes. In the view point of design spiral, it is desirable to generate finite element meshes automatically.

In the present paper, automatic mesh generation was achieved by means of mapping functions. The fundamental is square orthogonal base was mapping to quadrangle field on the surface. And a finite element is formulated as a thick shell element, in which special attention is paid to anisotropic principal axes, which are one of the most important characteristic of composite materials [4].

In a laminate, as the properties of layers are very different each other, then it is necessary to analyze layerwisely. And it is also required to display and evaluate stresses about each layer. That is to say, a layerwise postprocessor system is required. It is made possible to display same layer extend over different stack sequences, in spite of discrepancy in layer numbers, in the developed systems.

ASSISTING OF MAKING TOOL MOLD

In general, large scale composite structures are made by using of male mold or female mold. Female mold method is the method which is available to get accurate surfaces of product. However it costs very high. If smooth male mold was used, outer surface becomes uneven, then product need to be puttied to smooth surface. It is required to make products with smooth surfaces by using of male mold.

In the developed systems, stacking sequences and layup areas are defined on mold surfaces. Then it is easy to generate surfaces which are offset from smooth outer surfaces with thickness of laminates. Figure 5 shows a schematic of relations between mold surfaces and lamination. It is available that an uneven male mold is made by using of numerical controlled cutting machine with the generated surface data. After lamination of every plies on the uneven mold, it hopes that product has smooth surfaces.

EXAMPLE OF DEVELOPED SYSTEMS

The result of a hull of IOR cruiser under uniform pressure was introduced and discussed for example of the developed systems.

Figure 6 shows a schematic of IOR cruiser which is made by using of another surface CAD system [5]. Figure 7 shows a output of the developed systems, when IGES data was read in the systems. The laminate was defined uniformly [0/45/-45]_s in the developed systems. A keel line was fixed as boundary condition and uniform outer pressure was loaded. After finite elements were generated and calculation, the results of longitudinal stress distributions in the 45deg. layer are shown in Figure 8.

As the calculated stress is exceeded allowance, lamination has to be changed as shown in Figure 9. The finite element meshes were changed as shown in Figure 10. Figure 11 shows distributions of longitudinal stress of each plies in the developed systems, which means that it

is possible to display same layer extend over different stack sequences, in spite of discrepancy in layer numbers.

After lamination design finished, offset surfaces are generated in the systems. Figure 12 shows a schematic view of offset surfaces on the local coordinates which are projected to hull surfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The new modeling of laminated composite structures is proposed, which is based on the concept that laminated composite structure consists of five stratum: fiber and matrix, lamina, ply, laminated structure, main structure. According to the new modeling, some prototypes of CAD/CAE/CAM systems was developed by means of object oriented language. the systems has been demonstrated. It has been shown that these systems are effective in the point of designing, analyzing and manufacturing of laminated composite structures.

REFERENCES

1. Miki, M., and Sugiyama, Y., "Expert Systems for Composite Design with Object-Oriented Language", Proc. Japan-U.S. CCM-V,1990
2. Bernardon, E., Lee, T. and Luby, S.C., "Composite Fabric Design Tool", Proc. 38th Int. SAMPE symposium, 1993, pp. 2077-2082
3. Kimpara, I., Kageyama, K. and Takatoya, T., "Development of Computer Aided Design Systems for Advanced Composite Marine Structures", Proc. Japan-U.S. CCM-VII, 1995, pp.709-716
4. Takatoya, T., Kimpara, I. and Kageyama, K., "Development of Computer Aided Design and Manufacturing System for Advanced Composite Marine Structures(3rd Report: Application of Finite Element Analysis for Anisotropic Laminated Materials)", J. S. Naval Arch. of Japan, Vol.178, 1995,pp.593-599 (In Japanese)
5. MacSurf Pro v5.3, Decision Japan Corp., 1995

Fig. 1: Relations between lamination and finite element in the ordinary system

Fig. 2: Stratum of laminated composite structures

Fig. 3: Flowchart of laminate design and process design for composite structures

Fig. 4: Relations between local coordinate and global coordinate

Fig. 5: Relations of laminates and base surface on male and female mold

Fig. 6: Schematic of IOR cruiser

Fig. 7: Output of graphical user interface when IGES data was read in

Fig. 8: Distributions of longitudinal stress of IOR hull under pressure

Fig. 9: Schematic of lamination plan

Fig. 10: Finite element meshes after changing lamination

Fig. 11: Distributions of longitudinal stress in every layer after changing lamination

Fig. 12: Schematic of male mold surface in local coordinate